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Chief editorS.

G. Ahmed

Professor of Computational Mathematics and Numerical Analysis Faculty of Engineering, Zagazig University, Zagazig, Egypt, P. O. Box 44519

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*Professor of Computational Mathematics and Numerical Analysis Faculty
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PECULARITIES OF ENGLISH BORROWING WORDS IN TRANSLATION OF SOCIO-POLITICAL TEXTS INTO UZBEK**Rakhimova Kh.E.**

Master student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: The given article is related to the study of translation of the official documents into Uzbek language. The penetration and assimilation of English borrowings in Uzbek official documents are analysed.

Keywords: borrowings, English, Uzbek, socio-political, official, business, documents, assimilation.

Throughout his life a person learns to speak and acquires most of his skills from someone, say from his mother or father but he will also hear other speakers later on and learn some skills from them as well. All through his life the speaker will not stop borrowing speech skills from others, and these borrowings, though less significant, are very numerous and come from all sorts of sources.

E. Khudaykulov in his article states this fact that a word can be borrowed only when its meaning is understood by the borrowing language (Khudaykulov, 135).

"Borrowing - the process and result of transition from one language to another of words, grammatical structures, morphemes, phonemes; the most common type of language contacts". (Zheribilo, 107).

The relevance of this study lies in the fact that the history of borrowing more than any other area of vocabulary is closely linked to the history of the people in its relations with other peoples. Borrowing often shifts the meaning of a word. It also happens that a borrowed word gets its new meaning back to the language it came from.

According to the article by Davlyatova E.M. "In modern studies borrowed words are a specific system in terms of phonetic composition, structure, semantic load, so their correct use is difficult at first. Adaptation of borrowed words goes through several stages - phonetic, graphic, morphological and lexico-semantic". [Davlyatova, 355].

The purpose of this article is to consider and group some borrowings and their influence in the Uzbek language. It is clear that the lexical basis of the modern Uzbek language consists of several languages of the Turkic group and also, the history of emergence and development of the Uzbek language is closely intertwined with the history of its speakers.

We cannot overlook borrowings from Western European languages, especially English, such as: саммит, рейтинг, триллер, троллейбус, селфи, сквер, саундтрек, баскетбол, волейбол, футбол, бейсбол, гандбол, армрестлинг, бодибилдинг, допинг, керлинг, спорт, фитнес, старт, тайм, дисплей, ноутбук, принтер, сканер, CD, DVD, процессор, хакер, сайт, блог, логин, дисплей, ноутбук, Фастфуд, хот дог, джем, крекер, пудинг, Аутсорсинг, бренд, брокер, дедлайн, дилер, инвестор, лизинг, менежмент, пиар, прайз-лист, релиз, риелтор, стартап, холдинг.

Borrowing of lexical units - one of the prime examples of the interaction of the languages and cultures, creation of the general values. No such language, which had not unoriginal words. There is, however, such languages, which played and play the greater role in spreading the words, mainly - research and public-political terminology. In past such role in Europe played Greek and Latin, but later French and German languages.

Presently, such role executes, first of all, English and Russian (Koduhov, 188-201).

Borrowing of lexical units can occur spoken and written way. In the event of borrowing by spoken way, the words are completely assimilated in language. The borrowings which came by writing, mostly save their own phonetic, spelling and grammatical particularities. L.P.Krysin considered that borrowing in language be reproduced phonetic and morphological facility of one language of the morphemes, words or word-combinations of the other language (Krysin, 65 ?73).

M.A. Breiter notes that about 15% of the latest English words are borrowed due to the lack of a corresponding name in the receiving language. They include: "детектор" (валют), топ-модель, виртуал, инвестор, дайджест, спонсор, спрей. These borrowings also include those borrowings that, for some reason (easier to pronounce, in short, more specifically in terms of semantics) supplanted previously mastered or original Russian language units, for example прайс-лист (instead of прејскурант), имидж (instead of образ) (Breiter, 113-127).

Provider - (English: provide "таъминламок") is an organisation that provides services for the use of global networks and systems. Example: Интернетга уланиш учун провайдерингизга мурожаат қилишингиз керак.

We are used to turning on the radio or television in the morning and hearing the phrase: "Heads of state are meeting for a summit". There is an Uzbek equivalent of this word: музокаралар.

Имидж (услуг)- 1) the image of a businessman, the perception of a businessman by others, the reputation of a businessman. 2) the image of a company, goods, services, providing the position of the company on the market, the loyalty of the buyer to the brand.

There is perhaps no more popular foreign-language word at the present stage than the word corruption, although its Uzbek equivalent is probably no less common: пора. Example: Until we eradicate corruption, we cannot build a normal democratic society. - Коррупцияни йўқ қилмагунимизча, биз нормал демократик жамият қура олмаимиз.

The English have identified a number of styles of literary language: the official-business style, the style of science and technology, newspaper and journalistic style, the style of everyday communication.

Official-business style (language of diplomacy, laws, business papers, business correspondence) is equal in rights with other styles and plays an important role in formation and development of literary language. The features of official - business style are the objective fact of language, their application in the texts of the documents naturally and is fixed by tradition. The infringement of functional - style norm is considered when used language means, inherent in business style, which contradict the requirement of logicity, accuracy and brevity of language of business papers and documents.

As professor I.R. Galperin mentioned: "Official documents are written in a formal, "cold" or matter-of-fact style of speech. The style of official documents, or 'officialese' as it is sometimes called, is not homogeneous and is represented by the following sub-styles, or varieties:

- 1.The language of business documents;
- 2.The language of legal documents;
- 3.The language of diplomacy;
- 4.The language of military documents.

The dialect of official-business style is exceptionally particular and may incorporate:

internationalisms, terms, professionalisms, non-terminological words, things and etc. Among them linguistic borrowings from other dialects play a vital part.

The infiltration history of English borrowings into Uzbek is closely tied with Russian dialect, which affected incredibly within the advancement of Uzbek lexicon at the end of 19th and in 20th century. The primary English words came into Uzbek through Russian. Presently English borrowing can be found in any circle of advanced Uzbek. Especially, official-business records of Uzbek language incorporate numerous English borrowings, which play an important part in learning foreign dialects. Official records can be great case of sources for etymological examinations, as they may show the precise time of their entrance, semantic, graphical and linguistic absorption in accepting dialect.

Analyses of official documents showed that, Uzbek language has borrowed many different lexical elements from English during its development, including international words and newly borrowed units: билль, стэндстил, демпинг, трэмпинг, инагурация, спикер, электорат, холдинг, импичмент and many others.

".... Хуллас, ушбу ҳужжатлар, шундай қилиб, инсон ҳуқуқлари тўғрисидаги халқаро билль бўлиб қолди".

"..... у ҳолда 40-моддада баён қилинган стэндстил бўйича ШХБ қоидалари бузилади".

"Демпинг ўзида мамлакатнинг маҳсулоти бошқа мамлакат бозорига "нормал қиймат"дан паст бўлган "экспорт" нарҳда тушган ҳолдаги нарх камситишини ифодалайди".

"Шунингдек, трэмпинг деб аталадиган, солинадиган ва қўйиладиган юкларни идишсиз транспортда ташиш очик рақобат муҳити шароитларида амалга оширилиши керак".

The analyses of official-business documents showed that, most of above mentioned English words already assimilated in the Uzbek language.

Students who deal with official documents should know the meaning and etymology of borrowed words in order to use them correctly and effectively, as they enrich their vocabulary and help them learning foreign languages.

So the actual circumstance requires: 1) Introduction in a revolution of new sources; 2) New approach to drawing up of the teaching - methodical manuals on the language of official-business documents.

In the sanction of the given problem the important role belongs to the research of the official documents of English-Uzbek correspondences.

In the last 3-5 years, the Uzbek language has been intensively replenished with borrowed words. Especially many words have entered the socio-political and economic vocabulary. This happens because the country has entered a new socio-political formation, as well as free market relations. A process of denationalization is underway, and an attempt is being made to carry out reforms in various spheres of life. Language always reacts quickly and flexibly to the needs of society. One can say without exaggeration that a linguistic explosion has occurred. But there is nothing to be afraid of, because borrowed words are the result of contacts, relations between peoples and states.

In conclusion, we can conclude that the most variable linguistic component, constantly changing, is considered to be the lexical composition of the language. This change, related to language enrichment, reflects different historical periods in the development of society. The process of enrichment includes, above all, the process of borrowing words from other languages. The development of science and technology, international

contacts in various spheres contribute to the inflow of new words into the language.

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